

Using the neutrosophic N-AHP method to prioritize variables and expert analysis

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Abstract. The study focuses on addressing a growing challenge in complex decision-making: how to prioritize key variables in an environment of inherent uncertainty and contradiction. In this context, the research explores the implementation of the neutrosophic N-AHP method, a variant of Hierarchical Process Analysis (HPA) that incorporates neutrosophic logic to handle ambiguity and indeterminacy in the evaluation of critical variables. Although traditional HPA has been widely used to prioritize options, it has been limited in contexts where expert perceptions are not clear-cut or are marked by high levels of uncertainty. This work seeks to overcome those limitations, proposing a more flexible and robust approach that allows integration of the inherent complexity in strategic and operational decisions. Through the use of the neutrosophic N-AHP, the study not only introduces an innovative methodology for expert analysis but also provides a powerful tool for prioritizing variables in a wide range of applications, from business management to public policy formulation. The results indicate that this approach significantly improves the accuracy and consistency of decision-making by allowing experts to express their judgments more completely, adapting to the reality of ambiguous decisions. The contributions of the study are vast: first, they open up new possibilities in research on decision-making under uncertainty; second, they offer practical applications that can be adopted in different sectors, improving the quality and effectiveness of decisions. In conclusion, this research not only advances the methodological field but also offers useful tools for those seeking to navigate highly complex scenarios.

Keywords: Neutrosophic N-AHP, prioritization, variables, expert analysis, uncertainty, contradiction, decision making, traditional AHP, neutrosophic logic, ambiguity, indeterminacy, hierarchization.

1 Introduction

Labor laws play a fundamental role in protecting and ensuring the job stability of workers in any society. These laws establish a legal framework that seeks to balance the relationships between employers and employees, granting rights and responsibilities to both parties. The influence of labor laws on job stability lies in creating a work environment where workers can be confident of the continuity of their employment and protection against unfair practices.

First, labor laws provide a protection mechanism against arbitrary and unjustified dismissal. They establish valid legal grounds for termination of employment, ensure that workers are not unfairly dismissed, and provide a sense of security in their jobs [1]. This protection is essential to enable workers to plan their lives and careers with confidence, without the constant fear of suddenly losing their jobs [2].

Furthermore, labor laws promote equal opportunities and non-discrimination in the workplace. These laws prohibit differential treatment based on personal characteristics such as gender, age, race, religion, or disability. This contributes to a more inclusive and fair work environment, where workers feel valued for their skills and contributions, without worrying about being discriminated against.

Labor laws also set minimum working conditions, such as the length of the working day, mandatory breaks, and regulation of overtime. By ensuring that workers are not exploited and have an adequate work-life balance, these laws contribute to greater job satisfaction and overall well-being. Workers can count on reasonable hours and adequate working conditions, which in turn promote emotional stability and productivity [3, 4].

In the area of collective bargaining, labor laws allow workers to join unions and negotiate with employers to improve their working conditions. This strengthens workers' voice in decision-making related to their work and provides the opportunity to reach agreements that support long-term stability. The ability to negotiate and reach collective agreements fosters a more harmonious and stable work environment [5, 6].

Labor laws play an essential role in protecting and promoting the job security of workers. These laws not only set minimum standards for labor relations but also reinforce workers' confidence in their jobs and fairness in the workplace. By regulating key aspects such as dismissal, non-discrimination, working conditions, and collective bargaining, labor laws contribute to the creation of a more stable, fair, and equitable working environment for all involved.

In Ecuador, labor legislation is designed to establish a set of guarantees and rights that seek to protect the interests and well-being of the country's workers. These guarantees ensure that employees have fair and safe working conditions. These guarantees not only benefit employees, but also contribute to a more fair, equitable, and productive work environment in Ecuador [7].

Job stability is a crucial aspect of the workplace, both for employees and employers. Ensuring a stable work environment involves compliance with a series of legal aspects that protect the rights and responsibilities of both parties [8]. Below are some of the key legal aspects related to job stability:

1. **Employment contract:** The basis of any employment relationship is the employment contract. It must specify the terms and conditions of employment, such as salary, work schedule, duration of the contract, job responsibilities, and other relevant aspects.
2. **Protection from wrongful termination:** In many jurisdictions, employees have the right to job security and protection from wrongful termination. Employment laws often provide valid legal grounds for termination, such as poor performance, misconduct, or financial reasons. In the event of termination, proper procedures must be followed.
3. **Severance pay:** In some countries, there is an obligation to pay severance pay for unfair dismissal or in specific circumstances. These compensations may vary depending on the employee's seniority and local legislation.
4. **Stability of fixed-term employment contracts:** In some places, fixed-term or temporary employment contracts may be subject to restrictions regarding their duration and renewal. Termination of a fixed-term contract may require valid justification.
5. **Trade union rights:** Workers have the right to join trade unions and participate in trade union activities to protect their labor interests and negotiate more favorable working conditions.
6. **Leave and work permits:** Labor laws often provide for sick leave, maternity or paternity leave, paid vacations, and other types of leave. These permits contribute to job stability by allowing employees to address personal situations without fear of retaliation.
7. **Equal Opportunity and Non-Discrimination:** Employers must comply with laws prohibiting workplace discrimination based on gender, age, race, religion, disability, or other protected characteristics.
8. **Occupational health and safety:** Employers are responsible for providing a safe and healthy work environment. This includes complying with safety regulations, providing personal protective equipment when necessary, and ensuring that employees are informed about occupational hazards.
9. **Work-family balance rights:** Some jurisdictions recognize employees' rights to request flexible schedules, teleworking, or other forms of work-family balance.

10. Personal data protection: Employees have the right to the protection of their data in the workplace and employers must comply with data privacy and security laws.

These are just some of the key legal aspects to ensure job stability. Laws and regulations may vary by country and jurisdiction, so it is important to check local legislation and seek legal advice to ensure compliance with all applicable requirements. In Ecuador, job stability is an important principle in the workplace and is supported by specific laws and regulations, including:

- Labor Code: This law is the main labor legislation in Ecuador and establishes the rights and obligations of employers and workers. It contains provisions related to job stability, employment contracts, justified and unjustified dismissals, severance pay, and other important labor aspects [8, 9].
- Constitution of the Republic of Ecuador: The Ecuadorian Constitution recognizes and guarantees the labor and social rights of workers, including the right to job stability. Additionally, it establishes the right of workers to collective bargaining and protection against arbitrary dismissal [10].
- Organic Law for Labor Justice and Recognition of Work in the Home: This law complements the Labor Code and establishes specific procedures for the resolution of labor disputes, including unjustified dismissal [11].
- General Regulations of the Organic Labor Law: This regulation provides additional details on specific aspects of the labor context and its application, including provisions on job stability and dismissal.
- Regulation on Unjustified Dismissal of Workers: This regulation establishes the procedures to follow in the event of unjustified dismissal and details the steps to file claims with the labor authorities.
- Organic Law of Public Service: This law regulates labor relations in the Ecuadorian public sector and establishes provisions related to job stability, hiring processes, and the rights of public sector workers [12].

The purpose of this research is to determine the influence of job stability on the guarantees that labor laws must provide and their effects in Ecuador. To carry out the study, the unstructured interview technique is used to collect data, as well as the multicriteria decision-making method Hierarchical Analytical Process for the selection of the most important variables to be analyzed. This method allows the measurement of both subjective and objective factors from numerical and verbal estimates, providing great flexibility in the analysis to be performed.

2. Related work.

2.1 Neutrosophic Concepts

Definition 1 : ([13,14]) The Neutrosophic set N is characterized by three membership functions, which are the truth membership function T_A , the indeterminacy membership function I_A , and the falsity membership function F_A , where U is the Universe of Discourse and $\forall x [\in U, T_A(x), I_A(x), \text{ and } F_A(x) \subseteq] -0,1 +[, y -0 \leq \inf T_A(x) + \inf I_A(x) + \inf F_A(x) \leq \sup T_A(x) + \sup I_A(x) + \sup F_A(x) \leq 3 +$. Note that by the definition, $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$, and $F_A(x)$ are standard or nonstandard real subsets of $] -0, 1 + [$ and hence $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$, and $F_A(x)$ can be subintervals of $[0, 1]$.

Definition 2 : The single-valued neutrosophic set (SVNS) N over U is $A = \{ \langle x; T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle : x \in U \}$, where $T_A: U \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $I_A: U \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $F_A: U \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$. The single-valued neutrosophic number (SVNN) is represented by $N = (t, I, f)$, such that $0 \leq t, I, f \leq 1$ and $0 \leq t + I + f \leq 3$.

Definition 3 : The single-valued trapezoidal neutrosophic number, $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \rangle$, is a neutrosophic set in $\mathbb{R}$, whose truth, indeterminacy and falsity membership functions are defined in [13, 15].

Definition 4 : Given $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \rangle$ two $\tilde{b} = \langle (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4); \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{b}}, \gamma_{\tilde{b}} \rangle$ single-valued trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers and λ any nonzero number on the real line, the operations are defined in [13, 15].

Definitions 3 and 4 refer to the *single-valued triangular neutrosophic number* when the condition $a_2 = a_3$. For simplicity, we use the linguistic scale of triangular neutrosophic numbers, see Table 1 and also compare with the scale defined in.

Table 1: Saaty scale translated into a neutrosophic triangular scale. Source [15]

Definition	Neutrosophic triangular scale
Equally influential	$\tilde{1} = \langle (1, 1, 1); 0.50, 0.50, 0.50 \rangle$
Slightly influential	$\tilde{3} = \langle (2, 3, 4); 0.30, 0.75, 0.70 \rangle$
Strongly influential	$\tilde{5} = \langle (4, 5, 6); 0.80, 0.15, 0.20 \rangle$
Very strongly influential	$\tilde{7} = \langle (6, 7, 8); 0.90, 0.10, 0.10 \rangle$
Absolutely influential	$\tilde{9} = \langle (9, 9, 9); 1.00, 1.00, 1.00 \rangle$
Sporadic values between two close scales	$\tilde{2} = \langle (1, 2, 3); 0.40, 0.65, 0.60 \rangle$
	$\tilde{4} = \langle (3, 4, 5); 0.60, 0.35, 0.40 \rangle$
	$\tilde{6} = \langle (5, 6, 7); 0.70, 0.25, 0.30 \rangle$
	$\tilde{8} = \langle (7, 8, 9); 0.85, 0.10, 0.15 \rangle$

For verification of the Analytic Hierarchy Process model methodology in a neutrosophic environment (N-AHP), see [13, 15-17].

2.2 Neutrosophic social choice theory

This subsection summarizes the main concepts of the neutrosophic social choice theory developed in [18].

Definition 5: ([18]) Let $a = (Ta, Ia, Fa)$ be a single-valued neutrosophic number with truth value Ta , indeterminacy value Ia and falsity value Fa . The *distributed indeterminacy form* (DIF) of a is defined as $DIF = (Ta - TaIa, 0, Fa - FaIa)$.

The DIF aims to distribute the result of indeterminacy regarding truth and falsehood, that is, it measures the degree of affectation of truth and falsehood, when indeterminacy varies.

Definition 6: ([18,19]) Let a be a univalent neutrosophic number. A *precision function* H of a is:

$$H(a) = \frac{(1+Ta-Ia)(1-Ta)-Fa(1-Ia)}{2} \quad (1)$$

Where for all a , $H(a) \in [0, 1]$. H is an order relation representing an information accuracy score of a . If $H(a_1) = H(a_2)$, then $a_1 = a_2$, i.e., they have the same information, whereas, if $H(a_1) < H(a_2)$, then a_2 is greater than a_1 .

Let $S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$ be a set of alternatives and m a set of individuals. Each individual declares his preferences over S , which are represented by an individual neutrosophic preference relation R_k , where $N R_k$:

$S \times S \rightarrow [0,1] \times [0,1] \times [0,1]$ and matrix $R_k = [r_{ij}^k], j = 1,2,3,\dots, n; k = 1,2,3, \dots, m$, where $r_{ij}^k = N R_k(r_i^k, r_j^k)$.

$$R_k = \begin{pmatrix} & r_{21}^k \\ r_{12}^k & \end{pmatrix}$$

The function H (called the *neutrosophic index* or *neutrosophic hesitation function*) assigns a_{ij} to each neutrosophic value a number in $[0, 1]$. Therefore, the *neutrosophic index* or *neutrosophic hesitation function* is defined as follows:

$$H(a) = \frac{(1+T(a_{ij})-I(a_{ij}))(1-T(a_{ij}))-F(a_{ij})(1-I(a_{ij}))}{2} \quad (2)$$

The matrix $R_k^H = [H(r_{ij}^k)]$, $i, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$; $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$. R_k^H is quasi-reciprocal if and only if $H(r_{ij}^k) \leq 1 - H(r_{ji}^k)$. If R_k^H is not quasi-reciprocal, we call it an irrational individual. Other definitions are stated in [19].

Definition 7: ([19]) : $S_i \in W$ It is called a consensus winner if and only if $\forall S_j \neq S_i: r_{ij} > 0.5$, where $r_{ij} \in H_\pi$.

Definition 8: ([20]) The average social aggregation function C is defined to calculate the order of S_i in the group to the extent that individuals are not against the option yes, using the following equation:

$$C(S_i) = \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{i \neq j} r_{ij} \quad (3)$$

Where $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

3. Material and Methods

The population of individuals selected for the study was made up of workers from different backgrounds. A total of 63 workers, aged between 25 and 50 years, participated in the study, of which 56% were women and 44% men. Additionally, the sample included 8 professionals in Labor Law and 2 university professors in the same area, as part of the sampling group to provide their considerations on the subject analyzed and provide information from a professional perspective. After being informed about the objective of the study, 100% of them gave their consent to participate and collaborate.

The study was conducted based on the actors from whom the information was collected. The fundamental legal aspects to guarantee job stability, determined from the survey carried out on the workers, are analyzed, examining the effect of a set of variables. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method is applied with the help of experts to determine the influential variables for the analysis.

In this section, the proposed NAHP+NSC method for the analysis of the object of study of the article is presented. The first element is defined for any neutrosophic triangular number $\tilde{a}$ as the triangular precision function of $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, a_2, a_3); \alpha a, \beta a, \gamma a \rangle$, which is the TA function defined as follows [20]:

$$TA(\tilde{a}) = A(\langle (a_1, a_2, a_3); DIF((\alpha a, \beta a, \gamma a)) \rangle) \quad (4)$$

This is the degree of accuracy of equation 6 calculated for the DIF of the neutrosophic number contained in $\tilde{a}$. The inclusion of the DIF follows the idea of, where the accuracy function H calculates the effect of indeterminacy on truth and falsity.

It can be seen that the reciprocal or quasi-reciprocal properties in NSC theory are similar to the reciprocal property in NAHP, from the perspective of the rationality of the decision maker.

The method analyzed consists of the following steps [20]:

1. The objective of the problem is established and, accordingly, the group of experts is selected. Attributes, sub-attributes and alternatives are then specified.
2. The expert group is divided into M interest subgroups, denoted by $IG = \{IG_1, IG_2, \dots, IG_M\}$. In the analysis, it is assumed that the members of each subgroup form a homogeneous decision group.
3. Each expert evaluates his/her own NAHP. However, for each IG_i , the equivalent matrices of the subgroup members are aggregated using formula 5.

Given $\{\tilde{A}_i, \tilde{V}_i, \dots, \tilde{A}_i, \tilde{V}_i\}$ as a set of n_i SVTNNs representing the evaluation of each member of the i -th subgroup, where $\tilde{A}_{ij} = \langle (a_{ij}, a_{ij}, a_{ij}); \alpha \tilde{a}_{ij}, \beta \tilde{a}_{ij}, \gamma \tilde{a}_{ij} \rangle$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, M$) ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n_i$), the weighted average of the SVTNNs is calculated using the following equation:

$$\tilde{A}_i = \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \lambda_{ij} \tilde{A}_{ij} \quad (5)$$

where λ_{ij} is the weight of $\tilde{A}_{ij}$, $\lambda_{ij} \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \lambda_{ij} = 1$.

Note that λ_{ij} measures the relative importance of the j -th expert in the i -th subgroup.

Each $\tilde{A}_i$ represents the pairwise comparison matrix of the NAHP method in IG_i , to aggregate the pairwise comparison matrices of criteria, subcriteria and alternatives.

$\tilde{A}_i$ is converted to $\tilde{A}_i$ using equation 13. This process can be repeated until the results are consistent according to the consistency index of the NAHP method. According to this method, a preference vector of the alternatives is obtained.

Individual judgment aggregation (IJA) is used here because there is interest in measuring the subgroup judgments as a synergistic unit.

Let be $O_i = \{O_{i1}, O_{i2}, \dots, O_{iN}\}$ the position of each alternative when evaluated by the members of the i -th subgroup. For example, $O_1 = \{1, 1, 3, 5, 4\}$ means that according to the first subgroup, alternatives 1 and 2 are equally preferred, while subsequent alternatives are the third, fifth, and fourth alternatives, in that order.

4. For each $S_{il} (l = 1, 2, \dots, N)$, V_{il} the following triplet is formed $P_{il} = \text{card} (\{k \neq l: S_{il} = (P_{il}, I_{il}, N_{il}) \text{ is strictly preferable to } S_{ik}\})$, $I_{il} = \text{card} (\{k \neq l: S_{il} \text{ is equally preferred to } S_{ik}\})$, and $N_{il} = \text{card} (\{k \neq l: S_{ik} \text{ is strictly preferable over } S_{il}\})$.

It is observed that, $V_{il} \in [0, N - 1] \times [0, N - 1] \times [0, N - 1]$ and $P_{il} + I_{il} + N_{il} = N - 1$.

Finally, $V_l \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \times [0, 1]$, $V_l = (P_l, I_l, N_l)$, sums the l th alternative preference for all subgroups, where $P_l = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M P_{il}}{M(N-1)}$, $I_l = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M I_{il}}{M(N-1)}$, and $N_l = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M N_{il}}{M(N-1)}$.

Please note that this is a neutrosophic voting method.

5. $H(V_l) (l = 1, 2, \dots, N)$ and the alternatives are ranked by preference, such that V_{l_1} is preferable to V_{l_2} if and only if $H(V_{l_1}) > H(V_{l_2})$. When $H(V_{l_1}) = H(V_{l_2})$, then " V is considered l_1 equally preferable to V_{l_2} ". (See [20])

4. Results and discussion

The bibliographic analysis carried out on the subject of study, as well as the experience of the selected experts, allowed us to identify a set of factors that can influence job stability and the effectiveness of labor law in Ecuador. Among the most notable are:

1. Employment contract
2. Protection against unfair dismissal
3. Protection of personal data
4. Stability in fixed-term contracts
5. Trade union rights
6. License and work permits
7. Equal opportunities and non-discrimination
8. Safety and health at work
9. Rights to work-family conciliation
10. Severance pays

After several rounds of questions and processing of information through Delphi as shown in Table 2, with responses and adjustments to the data initially obtained, a consensus was reached to carry out the analysis with the variables shown, considering that they are the ones with the greatest influence and provide results of greater importance in the analysis of the research object in development.

Table 2: Delphi method. Source: own elaboration

Delphi	Expert 1	Expert 2	Expert 3	Expert 4	Expert 5	Average	Standard deviation
Equal opportunities and non-discrimination	8	7	9	8	7	7.8	0.74833147
Employment contract	7	8	8	9	7	7.8	0.74833147
Protection against unfair dismissal	9	9	10	8	9	9	0.63245553
Health and safety at work	8	9	7	8	8	8	0.63245553
License and work permits	8	8	9	7	8	8	0.63245553
Severance pay	5	5	6	5	4	5	0.63245553
Stability in fixed-term contracts	10	9	10	9	10	9.6	0.48989794
Trade union rights	7	8	8	7	7	7.4	0.48989794
Protection of personal data	6	7	7	6	6	6.4	0.48989794
Rights to work-family conciliation	6	5	5	6	6	5.6	0.48989794

For the specific situations that occur most frequently and contravene labor legislation, the following measures or alternatives are proposed to analyze the level of influence and decision-making that favor the protection of labor rights:

1. Clear contractual conditions. (Review the terms and stipulations of the contract to protect against unfair dismissal)
2. Stability period. (Provide protection to the worker ensuring compliance during the time stipulated in the contract)
3. Administrative advice. (Through proper guidance from management, the employee can perform his/her work without difficulty)
4. Flexible negotiation. (Facilitate flexible adaptation of terms and conditions as necessary through mutual agreement between the contracted individual and the employer)
5. Supervision. (Contracted personnel must be periodically supervised by management to provide information and guidance aimed at improving the quality of service.)
6. Working conditions. (Minimum conditions necessary for carrying out the work must be provided, guaranteed by management)

Once the variables to be analyzed have been obtained, the experts are asked to make pairwise comparisons between them, so that it can be determined which ones have the greatest influence on the others concerning labor law. Once the individual assessments of all the experts have been obtained, an average of all the assessments is calculated. The result obtained from the analysis is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Pairwise comparison matrix. Source: Own elaboration.

N-AHP	Clear contractual conditions	Stability time	Administrative advice	Flexible negotiation	Supervision	Working conditions
Clear contractual conditions	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{7}$	$\tilde{7}$	$\tilde{7}$	$\tilde{8}$	$\tilde{6}$
Period of stability	$\frac{1}{\tilde{7}}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{5}$	$\tilde{4}$	$\tilde{7}$
Administrative advice	$\frac{1}{\tilde{7}}$	$\frac{1}{\tilde{3}}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{3}$	$\tilde{3}$
Flexible negotiation	$\frac{1}{\tilde{7}}$	$\frac{1}{\tilde{5}}$	$\frac{1}{\tilde{3}}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{3}$
Supervision	$\frac{1}{\tilde{8}}$	$\frac{1}{\tilde{4}}$	$\frac{1}{\tilde{3}}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{1}$
Working conditions	$\frac{1}{\tilde{6}}$	$\frac{1}{\tilde{7}}$	$\frac{1}{\tilde{3}}$	$\frac{1}{\tilde{3}}$	$\tilde{1}$	$\tilde{1}$

Figure 1. Heat map of the weighted matrix. Source: Own elaboration using scoring equation.

In Figure 1, each cell shows the relative importance of one criterion compared to another, with colors indicating the degree of importance: darker shades of blue represent higher values, while lighter shades indicate lower values. As can be seen, the weighted combination of 0.3 is the highest value and 0.03 is the lowest combination. The weight of each was then determined, as shown in Figure 2. After developing the

pairwise comparison matrix and continuing with the logic of the method, the weight vector of each of the factors analyzed in the consistency study is obtained, with an eigenvalue of 0.2815358, an IC coefficient of 0.06, and a CR of 0.04, which is considered consistent and therefore valid for the study.

Figure 2: Weighting of criteria according to the N-AHP method. Source: Own elaboration

The image shows a horizontal bar chart representing the weights of various criteria in an AHP-N analysis. The criteria evaluated include "Clear contractual conditions", "Stability period", "Management advice", "Flexible negotiation", "Supervision" and "Working conditions". Each bar represents the relative weight of these criteria, indicating their importance in the overall decision or evaluation.

The weights range from 0.07 to 0.25, showing a clear differentiation between the most and least important criteria. "Stability period" and "Administrative advice" have the highest weight (0.25), indicating that they are considered very important in this analysis. On the other hand, "Working conditions" has the lowest weight (0.07), suggesting that although it is still important, it has less influence on the outcome of the analysis compared to the other criteria.

By applying these results to decision theory data, it can be verified that in a second iteration of data processing, the following weight vector $P = [0.533, 0.209, 0.110, 0.058, 0.049, 0.039]$ is obtained, with the following order:

1. Clear contractual conditions
2. Period of stability
3. Administrative advice
4. Flexible negotiation
5. Supervision
6. Working conditions

As can be seen, there is a slight variation in the order, but the first three parameters remain the same. Therefore, it can be said that evaluating the effectiveness of labor legislation in terms of job stability involves analyzing a series of factors that can influence the way in which legal provisions are implemented and complied with in practice. The study revealed that for workers, aspects such as protection against dismissal, contractual relations and equal opportunities are essential to maintaining a safe work environment that allows them to feel supported by labor laws. [16,18,19]

Other key elements that influence the evaluation of the effectiveness of labor legislation on job stability in Ecuador are its compliance and application, since its effectiveness depends largely on its proper and consistent compliance and application. It should be assessed whether labor authorities have the resources and capacity to monitor and ensure that both employers and workers comply with the provisions related to job stability.

The clarity and accessibility of procedures and processes related to job stability are crucial. If workers and employers do not understand how to file complaints, claims for unfair dismissal, or how to conduct

collective bargaining processes, the effectiveness of the law will be compromised. Workers must have effective access to dispute resolution mechanisms and impartial judicial systems in the event of labor disputes. [20] The ease and effectiveness of these mechanisms will influence how issues related to job stability are addressed and resolved.

Labor legislation should provide clear and proportionate sanctions for non-compliance. The consequences of violating provisions relating to job stability should be significant enough to deter employers from taking unjustified measures. Both employers and employees should be informed about their rights and obligations regarding job stability. Education and awareness about labour legislation can help prevent misunderstandings and conflicts.

Overall economic conditions and job prospects can influence job stability. When economic conditions are precarious, employers may face financial difficulties that could affect employees' job stability. A country's broader economic and labor policies can affect job stability. An emphasis on sustainable economic development and employment promotion can support stability in the labor market.

A country's employment culture can influence how employment relations are handled. A corporate culture that values employees and an active union culture can contribute to job stability. Reforms and changes in labor laws can have a significant impact on job stability. It is essential to assess how these reforms are implemented and how they fit with the changing needs of workers and employers. Active involvement of employers, workers, and their representatives in formulating and revising labor policies can improve the effectiveness of laws related to job stability. Ultimately, assessing the effectiveness of labor legislation in terms of job stability is a multifaceted process that requires a detailed analysis of how legal provisions are implemented and adapted to the labor reality of a specific country [24,25].

5. Conclusion

This article has explored the impact of job stability on the effectiveness of labor legislation in Ecuador. Through the analysis and synthesis of information, it has been shown that job stability is an important aspect in the workplace, both for employees and employers. Labor legislation plays a fundamental role in protecting and promoting job stability by establishing standards that ensure fair and safe working conditions for workers. Through observation, analytical analysis, synthesis, inductive and deductive methods, and historical-logical analysis, various legal aspects that contribute to job stability have been examined in depth.

Mathematical methods of information processing, combined in a neutrosophic environment, effectively prioritize variables in the decision-making process, and experts in the field have participated in the identification of the most influential variables in job stability. The results of this analysis have revealed that the employment contract and protection against unjustified dismissal are the most influential variables in job stability, followed by equal opportunities and non-discrimination, as well as safety and health at work.

The study also highlighted the importance of compliance and effective enforcement of labor laws, the existence of clear and accessible procedures, access to justice, adequate sanctions for non-compliance, and education and awareness of labor rights and obligations. It emphasized how the effectiveness of labor legislation is interconnected with socio-economic, political and cultural factors, and how legislative reforms and social dialogue are essential to maintaining effective labor stability.

Labor laws in Ecuador guarantee fair and safe working conditions, and key aspects such as the employment contract, protection against unjustified dismissal, equal opportunities and job security are essential for job stability.

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